

MEDIA'S IMPACT ON SOCIETY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract:

Man is a social animal who cannot exist in isolation, his activities impact not just him but society as a whole, and society has an impact on a man in a variety of ways. Various media impacts on the person, his family, and society are emphasized. It is a requirement for living fulfilment, regardless of its imperfections and tyrannies throughout human history. Society is the entity in charge of ensuring that each person's life is satisfied. Every man has fought with one or more challenges in every culture. Media is the plural form of the word medium. Media are the vehicles or channels to broadcast information, entertainment, news, education, or promotional messages. Television, radio, newspapers, billboards, mail, telephone, fax, and the internet are examples of broadcasting and narrowcasting media (the primary means of mass communication). In this context, the present article investigates the influence of the media on society.

Key Words: Society, Media, Impacts of media on society

Introduction:

The media and society have a symbiotic connection. Although society has existed for millions of years and media, particularly the mass media, has only been for a little over a century, they both rely on each other for survival. The existence and expansion of civilization depend on various elements: a communication system, since members of society, get knowledge, education, and enjoyment via communication. The media, particularly the news media, has influenced policy and challenged people in positions of power in the public interest, thereby serving as the watchdog in a democracy. The public expects new media to take up problems on their behalf, express a popular opinion, and set the agenda for discussion and debate. Many opponents see the news media as a powerful institution since it has become prevalent over time. In reality, depending on who is speaking, each argument in the media oscillates between two extremes. Some individuals feel that media has unchecked power, while others believe that media has little impact on people's lives. Whatever one's point of view, there is no denying that media has become an integral part of the typical person's daily existence. Though the news may be intriguing or even entertaining, its fundamental purpose is to empower well-informed individuals. Journalism aims to provide people with the information they need to make the best decisions for their lives, communities, cultures, and governments. The four kinds of journalistic roles-normative, cognitive, practiced, and narrative roles-represent fundamentally different ideas: what journalists should do, wish to do, do in practice, and believe they do. The function of media in development, according to Wilbur Schramm, may be split into three parts: (i) to inform, (ii) to instruct, and (iii) to participate.

To inform: the primary prerequisites for societal growth are proper social, political, and economic impact. This information should be national as well as international. People should be aware of the difficulties or realities that limit their ability to progress.

To educate: Mass literacy is a critical component of development. It may be accomplished by instilling fundamental skills in the population. The media has a crucial part in this. The media can be used to inform and educate people. Two examples of how media may be used to instruct, educate, and teach people essential skills are Educational Television and Gyan Darshan. Learning these core skills may help people enhance their quality of life.

To participate: The country's total growth requires the citizens' voluntary and consistent engagement. In a liberal society, such participation is possible. Debate, controversy, and conversation may help people become more conscious. People may learn about current concerns, engage in developmental programmes, and influence society's quality of life through participating in discussions and debates. The media is a vital channel of communication that assists in transferring knowledge, debunking false ideas, correcting wrong or outdated information, and moulding public opinion, all of which may influence international politics. Historically, the media has been used as a tool of the people to combat feudal oppression. The media has had a significant influence on the transformation of feudal civilizations into modern societies, with the most significant impact in the Western world. The media has always been on the side of the people during times of war, keeping them informed about the future of international politics.

Objective of the Study:

- To find out the media impact on society development.

Methodology:

The present article studied based on descriptive method of research. The data was collected from secondary data sources i.e., books, journals and open access sources.

Media Impact on Society:

During the Indian National Movement, the media played a critical role in raising public awareness of colonial authority. By transmitting news on the advancement of the nationalist movement in India, it was one of the sources that led to the success of large mass movements against colonialism. The media, especially the free press, played a critical role in forming the Republic of India after independence. Without a free press and media, a democratic state, particularly in India, would be unimaginable. Poverty, famine, sectarian strife, partisanship, and refugee concerns were all handed down to free India to reward its hard-won independence from foreign rule. India is now on the verge of becoming a mighty nation. Previous and present governments have worked hard to restore India's image as a developed economy with a rich culture and heritage. India's achievements in science, technology, and the arts have been widely publicised, thanks mainly to the media. India is still categorised as a developing nation, despite its many achievements. In this circumstance, I believe the media can play a critical role in tackling the social, cultural, and economic concerns that have pushed India into the developing nation category.

Our country is significant in terms of territory, 0.32 per cent larger than Europe, and it has a highly diverse population, which differs according to colour, class, and caste. In such a setting, administrations find it challenging to adhere to democratic ideals while caring for each country resident, especially in smaller villages and panchayats. As a result, media outlets, particularly the small and medium press, are the only chance to expose the reality of rural India and act as a conduit for voicing their grievances. Rural communities and small towns have difficulties that are distinct from those faced by metropolitan areas. As the media grows in popularity in smaller cities and villages, it becomes their responsibility to meet the needs of the locals and bridge the gap between the ruler and the ruled.

Rural India, which accounts for 68.84 per cent of the country's population, is still fighting for existence, battling outdated beliefs spawned by casteism, communalism, perpetual poverty, and other societal ills. Valid, many segments of our society are still illiterate, uneducated, and blindly adhere to age-old beliefs and conservative views. As a result, it is critical that the media, particularly the press, introduces modern ideas to residents of backward areas, as this may aid in the eradication of superstitions and false beliefs such as honour killing, female foeticide, infanticide, and a host of other social evils, as well as the eradication of backwardness, the transformation of their thought processes, and the integration of rural India into enlightened India.

Social issues are afflicting rural India, but the rural population's financial capabilities are also a source of worry today. India is renowned as an agrarian country, with agricultural pursuits employing 58 per cent of the people. On the other hand, changing climatic circumstances in the region can result in significant losses for farmers due to crop failure. Because the majority of them cultivate entirely with rainwater, fluctuations in rainfall and the early or late arrival of winter rain directly affect the pace of cultivation, adversely affecting the financial status of these impoverished farmers. They, when unable to repay their loans, often commit suicide. This issue requires greater attention from the media, which may help improve the situation by informing farmers about new technological breakthroughs in agriculture and various government initiatives and assisting farmers in avoiding unpleasant scenarios. It may also serve as a watchdog, ensuring that all government resources earmarked for farmers are delivered appropriately and on schedule. Today's media must cover more social, cultural, and health-related concerns to contribute positively to people's growth and well-being. It must rigorously avoid displaying regressive ideals and notions that might lead India to the dark ages.

The media is primarily a service of current awareness, informing the public about current events, human activities, noteworthy natural occurrences, and other matters of public interest. It covers almost every subject conceivable and is geared toward a wide audience regardless of their level of experience or competence. The media may interest scholars, laypeople, professionals, scientists, artists, and musicians, among others. It has a significant influence on human life. In a democratic government, the Fourth Estate is the media, which shapes, influences, and indirectly directs public events. While the media lacks the constitutional power to regulate a state's affairs, it is an effective weapon for moulding public opinion on any issue under a democratic administration. It is critical in deciding what constitutes acceptable public policy.

The purpose of the media is to educate the public on current events, gossip, fashion, and the newest items on the market. A media outlet's goal must be to promote and trade products one way, without prejudice. It explains why people are spatially separated. The media claimed to be driven by principles of justice and fairness for both the common man and the affluent. Media outlets have a significant effect on society in several ways. The mass media enables individuals to acquire information about several issues, develop opinions, and make judgments about various subjects. The press keeps people updated and educated about what is happening in their communities and worldwide, and everyone learns something from it. However, media has developed into a narcotic for this generation since it has altered how we interact and are seen, both positively and negatively. It has both good and bad ramifications in the media industry due to the centuries-long effect it has had on generations. Certain types of false news affect society, creating crimes and encouraging individuals to respond rapidly and unthinkingly to a problem. Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp have all played a key role in recent years in India.

The media has the potential to shape people's attitudes and behaviours. For instance, we all have misunderstandings regarding leprosy and HIV/AIDS. You may have heard on the radio, seen on television, or read messages saying that we do not get HIV/AIDS via talking or touching a patient. Similarly, specific programmes and messages are promoted via the media to eliminate polio. As a consequence of the modification, things would improve. The concept of a country's progress is once again in flux, as obsolete technologies and equipment are phased out in favour of more modern, efficient alternatives. The media is critical in communicating this transformation. The media may help facilitate this transition by providing the necessary information and, in some instances, skills.

Positive Impact of Media on Society:

The following are the positive benefits of the media in social development. People rely on the media for news and information. The public can be educated through the media on many issues. The media aid a democracy's ability to operate. They educate the public on government policies and programmes and how they may benefit them. It allows citizens to express their concerns while also assisting the government in making required policy or programme adjustments. The media may entertain people. The media may contribute to the emergence of a changing society. The media has facilitated the interaction of individuals from all over the world. Advertisements in print and broadcast media promote trade and business. The media may aid in the political and democratic processes of a nation. The media may contribute to positive social changes.

Negative Impact of Media on Society:

The following are the negative impact of the media in social development. Media harms a country's traditional culture sometimes due to their programmes. The entertainment industry has become an essential part of the media landscape. It impacts the media's fundamental goals of informing and educating the public. The media encourages violence sometimes. According to studies, children are negatively affected by violence seen on television and in movies. The media influence people to want to acquire and possess items marketed in the media but it may not be necessary for them.

In my view, today's media, art, and literature in our society must help people change their thinking by providing a reasonable perspective and assisting the populace in developing a questioning mindset. Today, the media has become an integral part of our lives, and everybody relies on it for all of our daily news and perspectives. It's as technique for conveying information, thoughts, and ideas to a target audience, readers, listeners, or viewers. Because of the continual contribution of current technology to media growth, news transmission has become a simple affair, creating a significant chance for the media to play a great part in society strengthening. Its job is to keep people informed, educated, and entertained. The media has a significant social and cultural influence on society; as a result, it should function within and for society, reflecting the excellent image of humanity.

Conclusion:

Institutions, particularly political and economic institutions, have disliked the media's authority. Analysts say that the desire to control and regulate the media stemmed from a belief that the media may tamper with the reputation of the powerful and influential, particularly in politics and business. Legislative, executive, and judicial are the other three pillars of society, with the media being the fourth. It serves as an informer, an educator, a kind of entertainment, and an opinion influencer, contributing significantly to the well-being of society. To summarize, media communication plays a key role. The internet has magnified the functions, opening the way for improvement and increasing social significance. The media impacts several aspects of human life, including voting, individual viewpoints and opinions, and skewing a person's knowledge of a topic due to incorrect information. The media has a critical role in fostering a democratic society's health. It is the backbone of a democracy, acting as a connection between citizens and government. It keeps us informed of global social, political, and economic happenings. It's similar to a mirror, reflecting or attempting to reflect on the harsh realities of life. People rely on the media for critical information, especially in the form of news that may influence them. People may be alerted of difficulties and challenges in advance, allowing them to make better decisions about their future. In this way, media play a very vital role in the development of society.

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